

Experimental / Geometry

Experimental / Geometry

API Version: 1.0.0

Provide the geometry of the construction.

INDEX

1. COLLADA	3
1.1 GET /colladas	3
1.2 GET /colladas/{name}	3
2. POINT_CLOUD	5
2.1 GET /point_clouds	5

API

1. COLLADA

1.1 GET /colladas

List Colladas

List all the COLLADA files available.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
```

Array of object: Represent a COLLADA model extracted from a revision.

<code>name*</code>	<code>string</code>	Name of the COLLADA model
<code>revision_url*</code>	<code>string</code>	URL to BIM Sync revision from which we extracted the geometry.
<code>conversion_timestamp*</code>	<code>integer</code>	Time stamp when the geometry was extracted (seconds since epoch in UTC)
<code>md5*</code>	<code>string</code>	PATTERN: <code>^[a-f0-9]{32}\$</code> MD5 hash of the model

```
}]
```

1.2 GET /colladas/{name}

Get Collada

Download the COLLADA model.

REQUEST

PATH PARAMETERS

NAME	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
<code>*name</code>	<code>string</code>	

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Return the COLLADA model

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

undefined

RESPONSE MODEL - model/vnd.collada+xml

STATUS CODE - 422: Validation Error

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
{
```

```
  detail [{
```

Array of object:

```
    loc* [string]
```

```
    msg*  string
    type* string
  }
}
```

2. POINT_CLOUD

2.1 GET /point_clouds

List Point Clouds

List all the COLLADA files available.

REQUEST

No request parameters

RESPONSE

STATUS CODE - 200: Successful Response

RESPONSE MODEL - application/json

```
[{
```

Array of object: Represent a recording of a point cloud.

<code>name*</code>	<code>string</code>	Name of the point cloud
<code>mission_url*</code>	<code>string</code>	URL to the mission in which the recording was made
<code>recording_start*</code>	<code>integer</code>	Time stamp when the recording started (seconds since epoch in UTC)
<code>recording_end*</code>	<code>integer</code>	Time stamp when the recording ended (seconds since epoch in UTC)
<code>md5*</code>	<code>string</code>	PATTERN: <code>^[a-f0-9]{32}\$</code> MD5 hash of the recording

```
}]
```
